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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF UV-VISIBLE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF LAMIVUDINE AND ZIDOVUDINE IN BULK AND TABLET DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

Simple, rapid, sensitive, precise and specific UV spectrophotometric method for the determination of Lamivudine (LAMI) and Zidovudine (ZIDO) in bulk drug and tablet dosage form were developed and validated. A simple double beam UV spectrophotometric method has been developed and validated with different parameters such as linearity, precision, repeatability, limit of detection (LOD), Limit of Quantification (LOQ), accuracy as per ICH guidelines. UV-visible spectrophotometric method, measurement of absorption at maximum wavelength in 10 ml acetonitrile and volume make with water solvent system as reference LAMI and ZIDO were found to be at 271 nm and 262 nm respectively. The drug obeyed the Beer's law and showed good correlation. Beer's law was obeyed in concentration range 2-10 µg/ml for LAMI and 1- 5µg/ml for LAMI respectively with correlation coefficient was 0.999. The LOD and LOQ of LAMI were found to be 0.3831(µg/mL) and 1.1609 (µg/ml), ZIDO were found to be 0.6276µg/ml and 1.9018 (µg/ml), respectively. The proposed method is precise, accurate and reproducible and can be used for routine analysis of LAMI and ZIDO in bulk and tablet dosage form.

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INTRODUCTION

Reverse transcriptase inhibitors like lamivudine and zidovudine (Figure 1) ^[1-5] have been used in combination to treat patients with HIV. The treatment is used to prevent or prolong the onset of acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS), which can lead to a variety of fatal complications. Lamivudine is also used in lower doses to treat patients with chronic hepatitis B in whom the virus has replicated and caused liver inflammation ^[6-10]. Zidovudine is used along with other antiviral medications to treat patients with HIV. Zidovudine is also used in pregnant women to reduce the risk of HIV transmission from a mother to an unborn child. The literature review reveals that few RP-HPLC methods for the estimation of LAMI and ZIDO alone and in combination with other drugs ^[11-17]. As there is no analytical method reported for quantitative estimation of LAMI and ZIDO in combination, But the present study is to develop an accurate and reliable UV visible spectrophotometric method for simultaneous estimation of LAMI and ZIDO in tablet dosage form as per ICH norm.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents and Materials

A Shimadzu UV/Visible double beam spectrophotometer (Model 1700) with 1cm matched quartz cells was used in present study for multi component analysis. LAMI and ZIDO in the form of gift samples were kindly supplied by R. S. I .T. C, Jalgaon respectively. AR grade methanol used for UV method and 0.1N HCl and pH 6.8 phosphate buffer were prepared in double distilled water was used as solvent throughout the study. A combination of LAMI (150 mg) and ZIDO (300 mg) in tablet formulation was procured from local pharmacy (Duovir, J. B. Chemical Pharmaceutical Pvt. Ltd).

Fig. 1: Structure of lamivudine and zidovudine.

Preparation of standard stock solution

Lamivudine standard stock solution: (Stock I)

An accurately weighed quantity, 10 mg of LAMI was dissolved in acetonitrile in a 10ml volumetric flask and volume made up to 10.0 ml to produce a solution of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Fig. 2).

Zidovudine standard stock solution: (Stock II)

An accurately weighed quantity, 40 mg of ZIDO was dissolved in acetonitrile in 10 ml volumetric flask and volume made up to 10.0 ml to produce a solution of 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Fig. 3).

Preparation of Stock Standard Combination Solution :(Stock III) [LAMI + ZIDO]

Accurately weight and transfer 10mg Lamivudine and Zidovudine 40mg working standard into 10 ml volumetric flask as about diluents acetonitrile completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent to get 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ standard (stock solution) and 15 min sonicate to dissolve it and remove the unwanted gas, further an aliquots portion of LAMI and ZIDO stock solution in ratio of 70:30were mixed in volumetric flask in 10 ml and volume was adjusted up to mark with mobile phase from the resulting solution 0.1ml was transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark with acetonitrile : water (0.05% OPA), prepared in [5ml acetonitrile : 5ml Water (0.05% OPA)] solvent .Result as shown as; (Fig. 4).

Figure 2: UV Spectrum of Lamivudine. Figure 3: UV Spectrum of Zidovudine.

Figure 4: Iso-absorptive point of Lamivudine and Zidovudine.

Procedure for calibration curve of Lamivudine and Zidovudine:

The mobile phase was allowed to equilibrate with stationary phase until steady baseline was obtained. From the freshly prepared standard stock solution, pipette out 10mg Lamivudine and 40mg Zidovudine in 10ml of volumetric flask and diluted with mobile phase. From it 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5ml of solution were pipette out in 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to 10 ml with mobile phase to get final concentration 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of LAMI and 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of ZIDO (Table 1 and 2). The respective linear equation for LAMI was $y = 0.086x + 0.038$ and ZIDO equation $y = 0.070x + 0.049$ where x is the concentration and y is area of peak. The correlation coefficient was 0.997. The calibration curve of LAMI and ZIDO recorded at 266 nm as the graph plotted as concentration of drug versus peak area is depicted in (Fig. 5 and 6) respectively. ^[18-19]

Figure 5: Calibration curve of Lamivudine.

Figure 6: Calibration curve of Zidovudine.

Table 1: Linearity data for Lamivudine.

Conc. µg/ml	Peak area (µV.sec)		Average peak area (µV.sec)	S.D. of Peak Area	% RSD of Peak Area
	1	2			
1	0.1253	0.1239	0.12	0.00	0.79
2	0.2167	0.2146	0.22	0.00	0.69
3	0.2917	0.2914	0.29	0.00	0.07
4	0.3811	0.3912	0.39	0.00	1.85
5	0.47	0.471	0.47	0.00	0.15
Equation	y = 0.086x + 0.038				
R ²	0.997				

Table 2: Linearity data for Zidovudine.

Conc. µg/ml	Peak area (µV.sec)		Average peak area (µV.sec)	S.D. of Peak Area	% RSD of Peak Area
	1	2			
2	0.2011	0.2013	0.20	0.00	0.07
4	0.3211	0.322	0.32	0.00	0.20
6	0.4781	0.4736	0.48	0.00	0.67
8	0.619	0.621	0.99	0.00	0.14
10	0.76	0.7511	0.76	0.01	0.83
Equation	y = 0.070x + 0.049				
R ²	0.999				

Selection of detection wavelength :

Standard solutions were scanned in the range of 200-400 nm, against 10 ml acetonitrile and volume make with water solvent system as reference LAMI (Figure 2) and ZIDO (Figure 3) were showed absorbance maxima (lamda max) at 271nm and 262 nm respectively (Fig. 4). If Two LAMI and ZIDO sample Interact with this point is called isobestic point. The detection of wavelength in isobestic point in 266 nm.

Procedure for analysis of tablet formulation

Weigh 20 LAMI and ZIDO in combination tablets (Brand name : Duovir (150:300) Cipla Ltd.) and calculated the average weight, accurately weigh and transfer the sample equivalent to 49.26 mg LAMI and ZIDO into 10 ml volumetric flask. Add about 10ml ACN of diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with diluents. Mix well and filter through 0.45 μ m filter. Further pipette 0.1ml of the above stock solution into a 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.(10 μ g/ml). The simple chromatogram of test LAMI and ZIDO Shown in (Figure 7). The amounts of LAMI and ZIDO per tablet were calculated by extrapolating the value of area from the calibration curve. Analysis procedure was repeated five times with tablet formulation. Tablet Assay for % Label claim for % RSD Calculated, Result was shown in (Table 3).

Figure 7: Chromatogram for marketed formulation.

Table 3: Analysis of marketed formulation.

Drug	Label Claimed	Amt. Found	% Label Claim	SD	%RSD
LAMI	2	1.99	99.88	0.01	0.06
ZIDO	4	3.99	99.75	0.01	0.07
LAMI	2	2.01	100.58	0.35	0.37
ZIDO	4	4.01	100.25	0.64	0.61

METHOD VALIDATION

The proposed methods were validated accordance to ICHQ2 (R1) guidelines for linearity, precision, accuracy, limit of detection, limit of quantification.

RESULTS

Linearity and Range:

The linearity of proposed methods were evaluated by linear regression analysis, which was calculated by least square method. Calibration standards were prepared by occasional swirling required volume of working standard solution 10mg LAMI and 40mg ZIDO 10ml of volumetric flask and diluted with mobile phase. From it 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5ml of solution were pipette out in 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to 10 ml with mobile phase to get final concentration 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 μ g/ml of LAMI and 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 μ g/ml of ZIDO (Table 1 and 2). Absorbance of the drugs was measured. Calibration curve was plotted between absorbance of drug against concentration of the drug. These results shown there was an excellent correlation between absorbance and analyte concentration of drug verses peak area is depicted in (Fig. 5 and 6) respectively.

Accuracy:

Accuracy of the methods was determined at three different concentration levels i.e. 80%, 100% and 120% in triplicate for each drug as per ICH guidelines. From the total amount of drug found, the percentage recovery was found in range of 99-101% (Table 4 and 5).

Table 4: Result of Recovery data for LAMI and ZIDO.

Drug	Level (%)	Amt. taken ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amt. Added ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance Mean* \pm S.D.	Amt. recovered Mean * \pm S.D.	%Recovery Mean * \pm S.D.
LAMI	80%	1	0.8	1.79 \pm 0.00	0.79 \pm 0.00	99.26 \pm 0.01
	100%	1	1	2.02 \pm 0.01	1.02 \pm 0.01	101.80 \pm 0.74
	120%	1	1.2	2.23 \pm 0.01	1.23 \pm 0.01	102.57 \pm 0.35
ZIDO	80%	2	1.6	3.58 \pm 0.01	1.58 \pm 0.01	98.66 \pm 0.37
	100%	2	2	4.02 \pm 0.01	2.02 \pm 0.01	101.00 \pm 0.60
	120%	2	2.4	4.44 \pm 0.01	2.44 \pm 0.01	101.9 \pm 90.55

Table 5: Statistical validation of recovery studies LAMI and ZIDO.

Level of Recovery (%)	Drug	Mean % Recovery	Standard Deviation*	% RSD
80%	LAMI	99.26	0.01	0.01
	ZIDO	98.66	0.37	0.38
100%	LAMI	101.80	0.74	0.73
	ZIDO	101.00	0.60	0.60
120%	LAMI	102.57	0.35	0.33
	ZIDO	101.99	0.55	0.54

Precision:

Precision was studied to find out intra and inter-day variations in the test method of LAMI and ZIDO. Intra-day precision was determined by analyzing three concentration in three replicate measurements of within linearity range of drugs on three different times in the same day. Inter-day precision was conducted during routine operation of the system over a period of 3 consecutive days. Intraday and Inter day Precision studies on UV method for LAMI and ZIDO which shows the high precision % amount in between 98% to 100% indicates to analytical method that concluded (Table 6).

Table 6: Result of Intra day and Inter day Precision studies on UV method for LAMI and ZIDO.

Drug	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Intraday Precision		Interday Precision	
		Mean \pm SD	%Amt Found	Mean \pm SD	%Amt Found
LAMI	2	0.21 \pm 0.00	101.00	0.21 \pm 0.00	101.00
	3	0.29 \pm 0.00	97.86	0.29 \pm 0.00	98.25
	4	0.39 \pm 0.00	102.23	0.40 \pm 0.01	102.00
ZIDO	4	0.34 \pm 0.01	100.00	0.33 \pm 0.00	101.67
	6	0.48 \pm 0.01	102.52	0.47 \pm 0.00	100.23
	8	0.61 \pm 0.01	101.20	0.62 \pm 0.00	101.88

Mean of each 3 reading for UV method.

Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of quantification (LOQ):

LOD is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantify under the stated experimental conditions. LOQ is the lowest concentration of analyte in a sample that can be determined with the acceptable precision and accuracy under stated experimental conditions.

Repeatability:

Repeatability studies on UV method for LAMI and ZIDO was found to be, the % RSD was less than 2%, which shows high percentage amount found in between 98% to 102% indicates the analytical method that concluded (Table 7).

Table 7: Reapetability studies on UV method for Lamivudine and Zidovudine.

Method	Conc. of LAMI and ZIDO (mg/ml)	Peak area	Amount found (mg)	% Amount found
UV Method for LAMI	4	0.3917	4.11	102.81
	4	0.3911	4.10	102.64
	4	0.3901	4.09	102.35
	4	0.3905	4.10	102.46
	4	0.3915	4.10	102.70
	Mean		4.10	102.59
	SD		0.01	0.19
UV Method for ZIDO	8	0.62	8.15	101.96
	8	0.6134	8.06	100.78
	8	0.6145	8.07	100.98
	8	0.6157	8.09	101.19
	8	0.6178	8.15	101.57
	Mean		8.10	101.30
	SD		0.04	0.47
		%RSD	0.54	0.47

DISCUSSION

The proposed methods for simultaneous estimation of LAMI and ZIDO in tablet dosage forms were found to be simple, accurate, economical and rapid. The method was validated as per the ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines. Standard calibration curves for LAMI and ZIDO were linear with correlation coefficients (r^2) values in the range of 98.25 – 100.23 at all the selected wavelengths and the values were average of three readings. The values of %RSD are within the prescribed limit of 2 %, showing high precision of methods and recovery was close to 100% for both the drugs. Results of the analysis of pharmaceutical formulations reveal that the proposed methods are suitable for their simultaneous determination with virtually no interference of usual additive present in pharmaceutical formulations. Hence, the above methods can be applied successfully for simultaneous estimation of LAMI and ZIDO in formulations.

The proposed method utilize two medium i.e. 0.1 N HCL and pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. The comparison of method with already published two methods shows that the developed method is more accurate and economic as compared to other two method further the method complies with detection of drugs as per their label claim also no further derivetization or modification in spectra is required so the proposed method can be said as simple accurate and economic as compared to other published method.

CONCLUSION

The developed UV methods were found to be more accurate, precise and reproducible. The analysis of tablets containing two drugs gave the satisfactory results. The statistical parameter of these methods showed good results. The recovery studies revealed excellent accuracy and high precision of the method. The methods were found to be simple & time saving. All proposed methods could be applied for routine analysis in quality control laboratories.

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